

The Design of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of Mueang District, Samut Songkram for Ecotourism

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Abstract—The main purpose of this research was to study how to communicate the identity of the Mueang district, SamutSongkram province for ecotourism. The qualitative data was collected through studying related materials, exploring the area, in-depth interviews with three groups of people: three directly responsible officers who were key informants of the district, twenty foreign tourists and five Thai tourist guides. A content analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data. The two main findings of the study were as follows:

1. The identity of Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province. This establishment was near the Mouth of Maekong River for normal people and tourists, consisting of rest accommodations. There are restaurants where food and drinks are served, rich mangrove forests, Hoy Lod (Razor Clam) and mangrove trees. Don Hoy Lod, is characterized by muddy beaches, is a coastal wetland for Ramsar Site. It is at 1099th ranging where the greatest number of Hoy Lod (Razor Clam) can be seen from March to May each year.
2. The communication of the identity of AmphurMueang, SamutSongkram province which the researcher could find and design to present in English materials can be summed up in 4 items: 1) The history of AmphurMueang, SamutSongkram province 2) WatPhetSamutWorrawihan 3) The Learning source of Ecotourism: Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest 4) How to keep AmphurMueang, SamutSongkram province for ecotourism.

Keywords—Foreigner tourists, signified, semiotics, ecotourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM is an important industry because it creates income for developing countries. Thailand realizes the importance of continuously developing its tourism industry. The country supports and promotes many activities and projects with advertisements and publications geared toward people who are in this area. Also, Thai people are beginning to realize the importance of preserving their tourism resources and supporting ecotourism. The Ministry of Tourism and Sports said 22.3 foreigners visited Thailand in 2012, with the Chinese (2.7 million) just topping Malaysians (2.5 million), followed by Russians (1.3 million), Japanese (1.3 million), Koreans (1.1 million), British (870,164) and Germans (681,566) [9]. This increase in tourists has boosted many local careers and income as well as helping develop the transportation, basic construction and public utilities in the local communities where tourism is important. The local

people are less likely to emigrate to other places with these improvements in their own area.

Tourism in Thailand was recently affected by the changing world economy and natural disasters. The Tourism Authority of Thailand has continuously encouraged Thais to understand their Thai identities and the value of their historical sites, culture and tradition.

The tourism resources have recently been moving toward sustainable tourism [2]. The ecotourism industry in Thailand has achieved this. At the present, there are many aspects to manage effectively including various signs to the important places. There are some problems to group of tourists which are not clear such as signs to tell ways, signs for educational information of tourism sources. The location signs are only in the Thai language which can make it difficult for foreign tourists to understand. The information shows that the Thai identity is extremely necessary and important as a tourism resource. The way that the identity of the tourism resources is communicated is very important to help tourists understand and learn these ideals [6]. These groups are important to Thai tourism resources at Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province. In this research, The Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province is identified by: The History of Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkham, WatPhetSamutWorrawihan and the learning sources of the ecotourism: Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest. These topics are useful for both the Thai people and foreign tourists. The important problems took place at Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province. The communication to foreigners in English is the least important [7]. These situations may reduce the number of foreign visitors.

For this research, the researcher chose the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province to be the research area. This area is very interesting to foreign tourists and helps them understand the Amphur (District) Mueang, Samut, SamutSongkram province. ICOMOS (The International Council on Monuments and Sites) tries to communicate new events in the communities and the past civilization at the same time [4]. This function was too plain for the both the Thai people and the foreigner's younger generations to learn. If the researcher had not explored the topic for this paper, it is possible the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province would not understand this important tourism resource. The researcher is an English teacher who is interested in finding the identities of Amphur (District) Mueang, Samut, SamutSongkram province and the

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II. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

- To study the data and analyze the identities of the Identity of Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province, for ecotourism.

To communication the Identity of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province, for ecotourism develop the sustainable materials as a communication some ecotourism.

III. MYTHOLOGY

The Design of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province, for ecotourism. This research is qualitative research. The objectives of this research are The Design of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram Province, for ecotourism.

A. Population and Samples

There are three groups of samples that are outlined in the following items:

- The key informant group in the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province is five persons: the chief persons and officers in the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province.
- The foreigner group is made up of ten people per day who visited Thailand. The researcher interviewed the thirty people for the foreigner group by the following criterions:
 - The foreigner group who had come in the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, Thailand more than one time.
 - The foreigner group who specially visited the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, Thailand, and did not go to any other places.
 - In this case for the foreigner group, if a group included two persons traveling together only one person was chosen for the interview.

There are also the following conditions:

- The age of the tourists interviewed is more than twenty years old.
- There are six tourists from Europe, seven tourists from America, four tourists from Australia, seven tourists from Canada and six tourists from Asia

TABLE I
GROUP OF KEY INFORMANTS IN THE MUEANG DISTRICT,
SAMUTSONGKRAM PROVINCE

General data of group of key informant	Gender		Age				Level of Ed.	
	F	M	25 30	31 35	36 40	45 50	B	M
Key informant group in Amphur Mueang, Samut Songkram province	3	2	1	2	1	1	1	4
Total	3	2	1	2	1	1	1	4

TABLE II
GROUP OF FOREIGNER TOURISTS WHO CAME TO THE MUEANG DISTRICT,
SAMUTSONGKRAM PROVINCE

Samples group	G.#		Age				Times		
	F	M	22 30	31 40	41 50	51 60	61 70	1	2
Europe	4	2	1	2	3	2	0	3	4
America	2	5	1	1	2	0	1	2	3
Australia	4	0	2	2	0	0	0	6	2
Canada	5	1	1	3	2	0	0	2	2
Asia	4	3	2	1	4	0	0	4	1
Total	19	11	7	9	11	2	1	18	12

TABLE III
GROUP OF TOURIST GUIDES

Samples	Gender	Age	Working experience	Total
Group of Tourist guides	MF	2536 354555	46 51015	2 6 11 10
	14	3 11	122	5
Total	14	311	122	5

IV. DELIMITATION OF RESEARCH PROPOSAL

During this research, the researcher conducted the study at the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, Thailand, to study the data to analyze the identity and communication at the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, for ecotourism. This study was conducted from October 2011 to September 2012 by triangulation methodology such as observations, asking questions, taking notes on the data and checking documents.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Literature Review was conducted on the theory of sustainable tourism, the theory of communication, the theory of Semiology and other research for the conceptual frameworks for the following items:

The identities of the Amphur (District) Mueang, Songkram province

- The History of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkham
- WatPhetSamutWorrawihan
- The Learning source of Ecotourism: Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest
- How to keep the Amphur (District) Mueang, for ecotourism

VI. RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

The researcher used the qualitative method for this research. The research instruments consisted of in-depth interviews, direct observation and content analysis of written materials with the details below:

The interview was used in the unstructured-interview with both the Thai language and English language. The questions were divided by sample groups into the following items: Interview for key informant group in the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I: General information of interviewees consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, and position at

the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province.

Part II: The Interview Questions are listed below:

1. The history of AmphurMueang, SamutSongkramProvince
2. WatPhetSamutWorrawihan
3. The Learning source of Ecotourism: Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest
4. How to keep the AmphurMueang, SamutSongkram province for ecotourism.

Interview for tourist guides had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I: General information of interviewers consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, position at the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province.

Part II: The Interview Questions are listed below:

1. How do you know the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province?
2. What is the identity of the Amphur (District) Mueang, in SamutSongkram province according to your own idea? Please give examples.
3. What do you want to communicate to others about the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province?
4. In what matters do foreign tourists recognize the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province?
5. How can you help preserving the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province for sustainable tourism?
6. What are your suggestions to promote tourism at this tourist attraction?
7. What are the problems that affect foreign tourists at the Amphur(District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province?
8. How do you keep Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkramprovince for sustainable tourism?
9. What are the big images of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province according to you?

A conclusion section is not required. Although a conclusion may review the main points of the paper, do not replicate the abstract as the conclusion. A conclusion might elaborate on the importance of the work or suggest applications and extensions.

VII. OBSERVATIONS

Observations were collected to provide a content analysis of written materials at the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province. They consisted of the contents analysis to communicate about the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, WatPhetSamutWorrawihan, Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest and nearby environmental areas.

VIII. RECORDS OF THE CONVERSATION IN A GROUP

A. Workshop

The data was collected from field trips and separated by each categorical variables topic of research.

B. Taking Notes

The researcher took notes at each interview and used equipment such as a recorder, a camera, etc.

IX. DATA COLLECTION

A. Survey Study

The researcher collected the data by reviewing of literature and documents related to surveyed areas and collected the data from literature that were related to surveyed areas of the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province.

B. Key Informants

The researcher had an appointment with the five key informants for in-depth interview at the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province.

C. Group of Tourists

The researcher interviewed the tourists who visited the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province by interviewing thirty tourists from Europe, America and Asia.

D. Tourist Guides

The researcher asked the five tourist guides the following questions in their interviews.

X. ANALYZING THE DATA AND WRITING THE RESEARCH REPORT

The researcher collected the data from the interviews, studied the data and the documents and analyzed the content analysis. The researcher used the data of interviews from key informants, foreigner tourists and tourist guides. The researcher took photographs and recorded the documents. After that, the researcher gathered the conclusion from the answers and discussions in a research report following the conceptual framework and the theories outlined in this paper. The researcher described the report and related information in the content analysis.

XI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This report analyzed "The design of English materials to communicate the identity of the Amphur (District) Mueang, Songkram province for sustainable tourism by the following four items:

1. The history of the Amphur Mueang, SamutSongkram province
2. WatPhetSamutWorrawihan
3. The Learning source of Ecotourism: Don Hoy Lod and Mangrove forest
4. How to keep the Amphur Mueang, SamutSongkram province for ecotourism.

The ecotourism has occurred because of the affections of the national resources [1]. It was a center of learning about natural resources, a pleasure to view the mangrove forest scenery, plants and animals including mangroves, cork trees and fireflies. They were found in Cembalos' research, 2010. And Bushel's 'research in Interpretation in National Parks:

Some Critical Questions. The communication for the natural resources found that the communication should be geared toward ecotourism and stress the knowledge and the suggestions in the natural resources crossing the cultural divide: Western visitors and interpretation at Ayutthaya World Heritage Site, Thailand. The researcher found that the communication should show the highlight, preparing the manual for services and giving the information to the information center [10]. Moreover, it should create leaflets and a CD of the Amphur (District) Mueang, Songkram province. The communication should show meaning and important things which were found in [8]. Reference [3] mentioned the communication showed the information and true facts. Offering every type of communication means that giving the information and presenting it to natural sciences and history classes. It made the tourists feel better and better understand the content. It increased the tourists' morale to protect the natural environments for local persons, tourist guides and government officers who were responsible the natural resources [5]. The communication in the English language is very important for the Amphur (District) Mueang, SamutSongkram province, for ecotourism. Studying the identities of the natural resources in the international language of English made it easier for the foreign tourists to understand the identity of the natural resources in Thailand.

XII. SUGGESTION FOR THE NEXT RESEARCH

This research can be applied to the next research on other natural resources or historical sites, tradition and culture where searches for the identity of local culture are needed any sites that is interested in ecotourism in the future would be a good location to study.

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